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Weapons of the Strong

Conspiracy Theories, Political Elites, and Media in Turkey

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Presentation

In the summer of 2013, a number of environmentalists began camping out in Istanbul's Gezi Park. Their goal was to protect the leafy square from plans to replace the trees with buildings, adding yet more concrete to an already dense urban neighborhood. The AK Party-run city government had overruled a historic preservation committee's decision to save the park and was proceeding apace with plans to reconstruct an old Ottoman army barracks on the site, with apartments and a shopping center in the new structure.

A rare bit of greenery in a city rapidly losing its leaves, Gezi Park quickly came to symbolize not just the loss of Istanbul's fresh air, but also the AK Party's domineering approach to governance. When police violently expelled the environmentalists, thousands of Istanbulites rose up in protest, quickly joined by thousands more throughout the country. The park became the spark igniting a nation-wide movement protesting a range of grievances, all tracing back to the AK Party's increasingly autocratic push for power. The party, which had dominated Turkish politics since 2002, was facing its biggest domestic political crisis yet.

Anyone hoping that the AK Party leaders would meet the protesters halfway was immediately disappointed. While security forces attacked the protesters on the streets, Turkish prime minister Recep Tayyip Erdoğan dismissed their grievances curtly, instead accusing them of being agents of a vast, sinister conspiracy to undermine Turkey itself. Erdoğan claimed that the protests were the work of an "interest rate lobby" (*faiz lobisi*), a foreign plot designed to damage Turkey's credit rating and thus exact higher amounts of interest on Turkey's foreign debt (Zalewski 2013). The security forces subdued the protests by the end of that

summer and the AK Party remained in power. This did not, however, subdue the conspiratorial rhetoric deployed by Erdoğan, the AK Party, or their allies in the media. In fact, this was just the beginning.

Since 2013, the government of Recep Tayyip Erdoğan and its supporters in the media have increasingly portrayed themselves as locked in a struggle against shadowy global forces bent on blocking Turkey's rise to historical greatness. Beginning in October 2014, Erdoğan expanded the interest rate lobby concept into claims that Kurdish forces in Syria were being organized by a mysterious "Mastermind" (*Üst Akıl*), and since then this sinister villain has been accused of all manners of 'crimes' against Turkey, from terrorist attacks to AK Party candidates losing local elections.¹ This Mastermind is described as a global conspirator that works to stop Turkey's ascent to greatness; but for all the certitude that he/she/it exists, there is little specificity in describing its identity or location. Pro-government journalists have seen the hand of the Mastermind at work in Washington DC and Tel Aviv, Pennsylvania and Kobane, Damascus and Tehran, and while Americans, the British, and Jews are most frequently implicated, to date there has been an inverse relationship between threat perception and specificity in the allegations. Rather than being a liability, this lack of specificity gives the conspiracy theory a flexibility that allows it to be used against all matter of political opponents, domestic or foreign.

This conspiracy claim has been the AK Party response to a wide array of challenges, whether in domestic politics, diplomacy, the economy, or security. Street protests against bad urban planning, the growth of Kurdish autonomy in Syria, inflation, downgraded credit ratings, terrorist attacks, even losing a local election: all have been blamed on a vast network of foreign agents out to block Turkey's march to historical greatness. AK Party politicians loosely outline the plot against Turkey in speeches and then pro-government journalists fill in the details in their columns and TV shows. This approach seems to have borne political fruit: according to a poll by the Turkish polling agency KONDA, carried out immediately after the protests, some 54% of the general public (and 82% of AK Party supporters) expressed the belief that the Gezi protests were the result

¹ See, for example, columnist (and presidential advisor) Ibrahim Karagül's series of articles alleging that Istanbul mayoral candidate Ekrem İmamoğlu's victories are the work of the global conspiracy: <https://www.yenisafak.com/yazarlar/ibrahimkaragul/-imamoglu-projesi-coktu-mesele-secim-degil-istanbul-projesiydi-2-adim-turkiye-olacakti-casusluk-terror-milli-guvenlik-eksenli-sorusturmalar-acilmali-bakalim-bu-sefer-kimler-amerikaya-kacacak-2050287>

of a foreign campaign against Turkey, with TV being the main source of information for those not involved in the protests (KONDA 2014).

While in the 1990s Turkey was seen as an outlier in the Middle East for its dearth of conspiracy theories (Pipes 1996), since 2013 Turkish conspiracism has become so pronounced that several articles (Carney 2018; Gingeras 2016; Nefes 2015, 2017) and at least two academic monographs (Gürpınar 2019; de Medeiros 2018) have been devoted to the topic. What was perhaps most remarkable about the turn to conspiratorial political rhetoric is that it emerged *after* the AK Party had already ruled for over a decade. Prior to 2013, the AK Party relied mainly on issue-based campaigning and the strength of the economy, winning elections by focusing on bread-and-butter issues like economic growth, housing, and health care. They kept the support of social conservatives through traditionalist rhetoric and some related policy, but they also successfully courted many liberals through vowing to promote civilian control over the military, European integration, peacemaking with Kurdish groups, and even improving human rights (Fuller 2008).

For the most part, the AK Party navigated these years without resort to conspiracy theories, albeit with some important exceptions. In 2007 and 2008, members of the AK Party endorsed a number of conspiracy theory-based court cases used by prosecutors from the Fethullah Gülen movement to prosecute their political enemies in the military and civil society.² However, in most contexts, the AK Party responded to political challenges using fairly traditional rhetoric, devoid of the conspiracy claims that would come to dominate their discourse starting in 2013. Why then did the AK Party change its political discourse from conservatism and pragmatism to conspiracism and paranoia in 2013? And why did it happen after more than a decade of successful campaigning without recourse to conspiracy theories?

² This was perhaps the one conspiracy theory that AK Party officials have directly repudiated: after relations with the Gülen movement soured, Erdoğan avowed that the AK Party was deceived and that these Ergenekon and Balyoz accusations were fabricated in a March 19th, 2015 speech to the War Colleges Command. <http://www.hurriyetdailynews.com/we-were-deceived-erdogan-says-accusing-parallel-structure-of-misinformation-79936>

The Argument

These questions resonate far beyond Turkey. The political upheavals of recent years have led social scientists to examine a topic long marginalized in academia, as in polite conversation: conspiracy theories.

The role of misinformation in the Brexit campaign and the American presidential election in 2016 shocked many observers on both sides of the Atlantic. The term “fake news,” used by Donald Trump to dismiss unflattering news coverage, has threatened to define an era, and the fear that societies are losing their shared sources of facts is growing. Scholars have begun to respond to these and other events with more research on conspiracy theories. As with many recent transformations in politics and society, the new structures of networked communication attract the most attention.

However, Turkey demonstrates the continuing importance of what communication scholars call the ‘legacy media’—newspapers (and their accompanying websites) and television staffed by professional journalists. While bots, troll factories, and websites like 4chan and 8chan serve to incubate and disseminate conspiracy theories, the Turkish case gives evidence that the corporate newsroom plays a major role in the decisions of political elites to promote conspiracy theories or not.

This article presents a brief case study showing a relationship between changes in the political economy of the Turkish media and the prevalence of conspiracy theories in elite political discourse. It argues that the AK Party elites largely refrained from reliance on conspiracy theories as a political tool until *after* cultivating a friendly media ecosystem. The underlying claim here is that (most) political elites perform cost–benefit analyses and will not weaponize conspiracy theories unless they perceive a favourable communications environment in which to do so. Politicians can attempt to use conspiracy theories as effective rhetorical tools against their opponents, but, in a critical media ecosystem, they will refrain from doing so because of the costs to their reputations that such allegations can impose.

Theorizing About Conspiracy Theories

As the term ‘conspiracy theory’ has been defined in a number of ways, I use a modification of a definition formulated by Uscinski and Parent (2014: 32): “an explanation of historical, ongoing, or future events that cites as a main causal factor a small group of powerful persons, the conspirators, acting in secret for their own benefit against the common good.” My intervention is to change “common good” to “interests of the in-group,” as much conspiracy theorizing sees threats against a particular group, such as white Christian Americans or Europeans or Sunni Muslim Turks, coming from an out-group.

First, why are conspiracy theories important? Democracy is premised on the idea that citizens have the means to hold their political representatives accountable for their actions (Przeworski, Stokes, and Manin 1999). In order to do so, citizens must have access to information about what state officials are actually doing, as well to correctly understand the political, economic, and scientific realities in which they operate. For example, a political leader might be perfectly accurate in describing her carbon emissions policy, but if a voter does not correctly understand the impact of carbon emissions, she will not be able to successfully hold that politician accountable for the impact of the policy. Political leaders may have incentives to hide information from the public in order to capture public funds, violate the law, or carry out actions that would be subject to criticism if publicized. In the parlance of information economics, secrecy allows state elites to capture informational rents, benefitting themselves and imposing a cost on citizens (Persson et al. 1997).

There are obvious dangers that a world with no shared source of information poses to democracy, as voters will lack a common frame of reference to debate issues and pursue a common good. The danger is not just for democracies, however. To cite just one tragic example, misinformation spread via Facebook contributed to mass violence against members of the Rohingya religious minority in Burma.³ However, it is in democracies where public opinion is usually most important, and misinformation can change voting behaviors and thus greatly affect the nature of policy and even the survival of the democratic system itself.

³ Specia, Megan, and Paul Mozur. "A War of Words Puts Facebook at the Center of Myanmar's Rohingya Crisis." *The New York Times* (2017).

Scholarship on conspiracy theories has unfortunately been muddled by a failure to distinguish between the ways that ordinary people create or engage conspiracy theories and the ways that political elites strategically deploy them for political gain. One major work on American conspiracy theories (Fenster 2009) argues that the conspiracy theory serves as a sort of epistemic weapon of the weak for marginalized communities, claiming that belief in conspiracy theories, even when factually inaccurate, nevertheless empowers non-elites and minorities in their struggle against political elites. However, this argument ignores the reality that political action is rendered more effective, rather than less, by an accurate understanding of political issues, their relative impacts on people's well-being, and the nature of the political process. In short, (accurate) knowledge is a *sine qua non* for political power.

Many works on conspiracy theories suffer from a focus on conspiracy theories as fundamentally the product of the politically disenfranchised, failing to pay adequate attention their use by the politically powerful as a form of propaganda unmoored from the burdens of evidence. At the heart of my approach to conspiracy theories, by contrast, lies the observation that political elites are, generally speaking, strategic actors capable of evaluating the costs and benefits of a given political strategy, including the use of conspiracy theories. Given this premise, there is a counter-intuitive aspect to political candidates using conspiracy theories in a democracy, rendering the question of why and when they do use conspiracy theories worthy of explanation. Voters who disbelieve a conspiracy theory would find a politician making such claims untrustworthy, unintelligent, or even insane. A conspiracy theory that does not gain acceptance would thus impose high reputational costs on the politician and open her up to easy means of attack by her opponents. Given the risks, one must then consider what factors would be considered to promote the chance of success when deploying conspiracy theories. Certainly, having an effectively independent and critical media would greatly increase the chances of failure for a conspiracy theory strategy.

The Turkish Case

The AK Party was formed in 2001 and won 363 out of 550 seats in the parliament in the 2002 election, albeit with only 34.3% of the vote, due to the number of older parties that failed to cross the 10% threshold. This victory was

mostly due to the public's disappointment in the older parties in the wake of the 2001 financial crash, an economic crisis that restructured not only Turkey's politics, but its media as well. The 1980s and 1990s was a period of economic liberalization in Turkey, and many holding companies emerged and acquired media groups, which previously had been smaller operations typically run by families rather than conglomerates. The acquisition of media enterprises served not just as valuable investments in themselves, but also allowed the companies to exchange favorable coverage for concessions from the state related to their other enterprises, such as construction and mining (Kurban and Sözeri 2013; Yılmaz 2015).

The AK Party came to power on the promise of pursuing the EU accession process with greater verve than previous governments, and EU-related reforms carried out under the early years of the AK Party rule did lead to some improvements in journalistic freedoms. However, as the AK Party-controlled executive branch consolidated its control over policy-making, supplanting the parliament, it used this power to reshape the media ecosystem in terms favorable to itself. Yılmaz (2015: 153–9) identifies three periods for media in the first 12 years of AK Party rule: From 2002–6, EU reforms helped promote a more independent media, albeit with some trends in the opposite direction; from 2007–2010, a pro-AK Party media emerged as the state took measures to punish journalists and media groups contradicting its messages; and then from 2011–onwards, the AK Party state carried out a major crackdown on the remaining non-compliant media. These periods, importantly, represent phases in the evolution of the AK Parties use of conspiracy theories.

2002–2006	2007–2010	2011–2015
Improvements in Press Freedoms	Cultivation of Pro-AKP Media	Accelerated Capture of Media
Press Freedom Score: 55–49	Press Freedom Score: 51–54	Press Freedom Score: 55–71
AKP Largely Refrains from Conspiracy Theories	AKP Supports Ergenekon and Balyoz Conspiracy Theories (2007–8)	AKP Launches Full Conspiracy Theory Rhetoric (2013–present)

Sources: Yılmaz 2015; Freedom House (freedomhouse.org)

The table above uses Yılmaz's periodization, showing it along with the deterioration in press freedom as monitored by Freedom House and showing the AK Party's use of conspiracy theories for each period. Note that the Freedom House scores range from 0-100, with a higher score meaning less press freedom.

We can see in this periodization that the stages in the AK Party's use of conspiracy theories were preceded by successful moves to subdue the media. In 2007, Turkey's second largest media group, the Sabah-ATV, was sold to a holding company headed by Erdoğan's son-in-law Berat Albayrak, with two state-owned banks supplying \$750 million of the \$1.1 billion purchase. After the purchase, Sabah quickly changed from a critical, center-left position to strongly pro-government (Freedom House 2014). That same year, Erdoğan launched a campaign calling for a boycott against Turkey's largest media group, Doğan Media. Then, in 2009 the government issued a fine of \$2.5 billion dollars over supposed tax issues, forcing Doğan to sell two of its main papers to a pro-Erdoğan media group, likewise changing their coverage.

The AK Party accelerated its takeover of the media in the wake of the Gezi Park protests in 2013. Most of the legacy media outlets were already either directly pro-AK Party or strongly intimidated by the time the protests broke out. A prominent example of the extent of the state of the Turkish media at the time of the protests was CNN Türk's decision to broadcast a documentary about penguins rather than airing footage of the Gezi Park protests. The fact that one of the supposedly more independent sources of news chose penguins over protesters led to the adoption of the penguin as a symbol of the corruption of Turkey's media (Öztürkmen 2014).

Conclusion

This brief article showed that in the Turkish case, political elites only chose to launch conspiracy theories after having created a legacy media ecosystem that would amplify their claims, rather than subjecting them to critical scrutiny. This is a significant finding in that it can help us better understand why in some countries, political elites have chosen to use conspiracy theories while in other cases they have not. For example, in both the US and UK, there exist powerful media sources owned by the Rupert Murdoch family that have backed up the misinformation and conspiracy theory campaigns of the Trump administration

and Brexit campaigns, respectively. While valuable research is being done on the role of non-elites and their use of social media and deep web sites like Facebook, Twitter, reddit, 4chan, 8chan and the like to create and spread conspiracy theories, the Turkish case helps remind us of the important role of political elites and legacy media in what many fear is the advent of the 'post-truth society.'

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